

PHYCO
DATABASE

Booklet

Cosmarium spp. & *Euastrum* spp.
(Charophyte, Desmidiaceae)
of Palangka Raya, Indonesia

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Phyco Data Base Booklet: *Cosmarium* & *Euastrum* (Charophyte, Desmidiaceae) of Palangka Raya, Indonesia

Based on the research:

Adam, C. 2022. Variety of Cell Size of *Cosmarium* spp. and *Euastrum* spp. (Desmidiaceae, Charophyte) from the Aquatic Environment around Palangka Raya, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia. *Jurnal Biota* 8(1):1-10 DOI: 10.19109/Biota.v8i1.8002

The data also published online and can be accessed publicly on <https://phycodatabase.weebly.com/>:

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Introduction

This booklet is an e-book version of the Phyco Data Base containing 10 species of microalgae of the genera *Cosmarium* Corda ex Ralfs 1848 and *Euastrum* Ehrenberg ex Ralfs 1848. The description and image of microalgae species in this booklet is based on the results of research conducted by [Adam \(2022\)](#) entitled:

Variety of Cell Size of Cosmarium spp. and Euastrum spp. (Desmidiaceae, Charophyte) from the Aquatic Environment around Palangka Raya, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia.

Table 1. *Cosmarium* spp. and *Euastrum* spp. of Palangka Raya, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia

No.	Genera	Species
1	<i>Cosmarium</i>	<i>C. biretum</i> <i>C. botrytis</i> <i>C. granatum</i> <i>C. trilobulatum</i> <i>Cosmarium</i> sp.1
2	<i>Euastrum</i>	<i>E. bidentatum</i> <i>E. denticulatum</i> <i>E. didelta</i> <i>E. pulchellum</i> <i>E. turgidum</i>

Source: [Adam \(2022\)](#)

Cosmarium Corda ex Ralfs, 1848

Cosmarium is one of the oldest genera of the family Desmidiaceae with approximately 1,026 taxonomically accepted species (Guiry & Guiry, 2021).

C. biretum *Fig. 1a (pg5)*

Cosmarium biretum Brébisson ex Ralfs 1848 is the only scientific name of this *Cosmarium* species that is accepted taxonomically, although there are 3 (three) synonyms of this species, namely *C. biretum* var. *triquetrum* Brébisson 1856, *C. quadrangulatum* Hantzsch 1860, and *C. biretum* var. *minus* Hansgirg 1888 (Guiry & Guiry, 2021). *Cosmarium biretum* has dark green color and the nucleus is clearly visible in the isthmus. Each semi-cell is shaped like a kidney and looks like two kidneys joined together with a closed sinus (Adam, 2022).

C. botrytis *Fig. 1b (pg5)*

Cosmarium botrytis originally described in 1840 by Meneghini has the homotypic synonym *Euastrum botrytis* (Meneghini ex Ralfs) Nägeli 1849 and 3 (three) heterotypic synonyms that are *Heterocarpella botrytis* Bory 1825, *Didymidium botrytis* (Bory) Reinsch 1866, and *Ursinella botrytis* (Bory) Kuntze 1891. *Cosmarium botrytis* is the only scientific name of this species that is currently accepted taxonomically (Guiry & Guiry, 2021). The semi-cells are joined by a narrow isthmus at the cell equator (Bellinger & Sigee, 2010) and appear to be

pyramidal in shape with rounded margins. The nucleus is clearly visible in the area between the two semi-cells (isthmus) (Adam, 2022). The sinus appears deep and linear straight towards the isthmus. *C. botrytis* is also noticed by the two pyrenoids that are clearly visible in each semi-cell (Adam, 2022).

C. granatum *Fig. 1c (pg5)*

Cosmarium granatum Brébisson ex Ralfs 1848 is the scientific name of this *Cosmarium* species that is accepted taxonomically and has two heterotypic synonyms that are *Euastrum granatum* (Brébisson ex Ralfs) F. Gay and *C. granatum* f. *pentagonum* Raciborski 1892 (Guiry & Guiry, 2021). *Cosmarium granatum* cell has 30 µm long and 24 µm wide. *Cosmarium granatum* cell is small, has green coloration, and the nucleus is clearly visible in the isthmus. Both semi-cells are pyramidal in shape with a rounded and truncate apex. There is a slight notch at the center of the apex. The sinus between the two semi-cells is slightly closed. The pyrenoids appear to be spherical in shape and clearly visible in each semi-cell (Adam, 2022).

C. trilobulatum *Fig. 1d (pg6)*

Cosmarium trilobulatum was originally described by Reinsch in 1866 and published in his paper in 1867 and currently is accepted taxonomically (Guiry & Guiry, 2021). *Cosmarium trilobulatum* has two subtrapezoidal and 3-lobed semi-cells (Felisberto & Rodrigues, 2004). The apex of each semi-cell is wide and truncate, sometimes with a slight notch at the

center region (Lee, 2015). *Cosmarium trilobulatum* is the smallest *Cosmarium* species found in this study with 17 μm long and 14 μm wide. The sinus between the two semi-cells is closed. The pyrenoids appear to be spherical in shape and clearly visible in each semi-cell (Adam, 2022).

***Cosmarium* sp.1** *Fig. 1e (pg6)*

Cosmarium sp.1 cell has 24 μm long and 21 μm wide. The semi-cells appear to be pyramidal in shape with wide and truncate apex. Pyrenoids are spherical and have a color that appears to almost blend with the cell's color (Adam, 2022).

Figure 1a

Figure 1b

Figure 1c

Figure 1d

Figure 1e

Euastrum Ehrenberg ex Ralfs, 1848

Euastrum has 304 species and infraspecies which are accepted taxonomically (Guiry & Guiry, 2021).

E. bidentatum *Fig. 2a (pg10)*

E. bidentatum was originally described by Nägeli in 1849. According to the database on Algaebase.org, it has homotypic synonym *E. elegans* var. *bidentatum* (Nägeli) J.P. Jacobsen 1875 and 2 (two) heterotypic synonyms namely *E. bidentatum* f. *bidentatum* Nägeli 1849 and *E. bidentatum* var. *glabrum* Grönblad 1942 (Guiry & Guiry, 2021). *Euastrum bidentatum* has 40 µm long and 27 µm wide (Adam, 2022). The semi-cells are divided by deep median constrictions (sinus); apical margin angular and with a wide incision V shaped (Aquino et al., 2017; Silva & Felisberto, 2015). The cell walls are ornamented with spine-like structures (spiniferous processes at the terminal angles). The ornamental pattern on the cell walls made this species look somewhat like *Micrasterias* (Adam, 2022).

E. denticulatum *Fig. 2b (pg10)*

E. denticulatum was originally described by Gay in 1884 and is currently regarded as a synonym of *Euastrum amoenum* F. Gay. *E. denticulatum* has two heterotypic synonyms that are *E. denticulatum* var. *granulatum* West 1892 and *E. denticulatum* var. *angusticeps* Grönbald 1921 (Guiry & Guiry, 2021).

Euastrum denticulatum is the smallest species of *Euastrum* found in this study with 24 µm long and 17 µm wide (Adam, 2022). The semi-cells appear to be subtrapeziform (Aquino et al., 2017) and semi-quadrangular (Silva & Felisberto, 2015) in shape, 3-lobed with a tiny spine at each angle as the ornamental features of the cell walls. Apical lobes appear wide with a deep V-shaped median notch. The sinus between the two semi-cells is closed (Adam, 2022).

E. didelta *Fig. 2c (pg10)*

Euastrum didelta originally described by Ralfs in 1848 and currently is accepted taxonomically. *E. didelta* has 4 (four) heterotypic synonyms, namely *E. didelta* var. *didelta* Turpin ex Ralfs 1848, *E. didelta* f. *ansatiforme* Schmidle 1898, *E. didelta* var. *ansatiforme* (Schmidle) F. Duceillier 1915, and *E. didelta* var. *cuneatiforme* Duceillier 1915 (Guiry & Guiry, 2021). *Euastrum didelta* varies widely in cell size among all *Euastrum* species found in this study. The cell length of *E. didelta* ranges from 50-71 µm and the cell width ranges from 32-42 µm. The smallest *E. didelta* cell sizes observed in the study were 50 µm long, 32 µm wide and 14 µm wide of the apex (Adam, 2022). The semi-cells are trapezoidal in shape (Silva & Felisberto, 2015) and divided by deep median constrictions that are almost completely enclosed with a slight opening at the end. The cell walls appear to be smooth without any ornamentations (Adam, 2022).

E. pulchellum *Fig. 2d (pg11)*

E. pulchellum was originally described by Brébisson in 1856 and is currently accepted taxonomically (Guiry & Guiry, 2021). *Euastrum pulchellum* has 29 µm long and 20 µm wide. Morphologically, *E. pulchellum* semi-cells look somewhat like *E. denticulatum* but with longer apical lobes. The semi-cells are quadrangular in shape with a tiny spine at each angle as well; the sinus between the two semi-cells are enclosed. The apical lobes appear wide with a deep narrow median incision straight towards the pyrenoid (Adam, 2022).

E. turgidum *Fig. 2e (pg11)*

E. turgidum was first described by Wallich in 1855 and published in his paper in 1860 (Guiry & Guiry, 2021; Scott & Prescott, 1960). *Euastrum turgidum* is the scientific name of this species that is currently accepted taxonomically (Guiry & Guiry, 2021). *Euastrum turgidum* is one of the largest *Euastrum* species found in this study with 89 µm long and 80 µm wide. In this study, *E. turgidum* cells were also observed after binary fission with asymmetrical cell shapes, 80 µm long and 38-80 µm wide (Adam, 2022). The semi-cells appear to be trapezoid in shape and are divided by deep closed-sinus. The apical lobe is very wide, straight, and truncate (Scott & Prescott, 1960), approximately 75% of the width of the cell (Adam, 2022).

Figure 2a

Figure 2b

Figure 2c

Figure 2d

Figure 2e

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